

An Updated Discrete Element Model for the In-Plane Behaviour of NFRCM Strengthened Masonry Walls

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Abstract. Masonry strengthened with natural fabric-reinforced cementitious matrix (NFRCM-strengthened masonry) is investigated by updating an existing discrete element model. Masonry walls are modelled by rigid blocks and elastoplastic interfaces that are able to account for mortar joints and block cracking. The reinforcement is modelled in a simplified manner considering perfect adhesion between wall and reinforcement and by adopting further spring elements connecting block centres. The model is validated by comparing it with an existing FEM based on a multi-step homogenization, where reinforced masonry is considered as a whole. Both approaches are used for performing nonlinear pushover tests with an increasing shear action applied to unreinforced and reinforced panels. The updated discrete model turns out to be able to represent the strength increment given by the reinforcement, but it is less able to represent the corresponding ductility increment.

Introduction

The assessment of FRCM-strengthened masonry is an active field of research and represents a complex task, given that both masonry and FRCM are composite materials. FRCM strengthening systems were introduced as an alternative to FRP in order to improve the compatibility of reinforcement with respect to masonry substrate [1]. Furthermore, in the last years, the attention to the use of eco-compatible materials and the development of sustainable solutions for strengthening has increased, leading to FRCM made by natural fibres (NFRCM, [2]). Focusing on standard FRCM systems, the numerical modelling of this strengthening typology has started in the last years. Some macro-models consider masonry components (bricks and mortar) as a homogeneous continuum, and the FRCM layers are considered as an equivalent continuum, with the textile fibres assumed as an embedded reinforcement of mortar matrix [3]. These models have also been implemented by reference to NFRCM [4]. In this work, an updated discrete element model is proposed for simulating the in-plane behaviour of masonry walls strengthened with FRCM or NFRCM. The model is based on an existing discrete/rigid model having rigid blocks and nonlinear interfaces that has already tested its reliability in representing unreinforced masonry behaviour [5]. This model has been recently extended for studying unreinforced and partially reinforced masonry arches, without focusing on reinforcement characteristics [6]. In this case, the proposed model is improved by considering in-plane loaded masonry walls strengthened on both sides by FRCM constituted by synthetic or natural textiles. The model considers as preliminary hypotheses for masonry walls rigid blocks and mortar joints modelled as interfaces; further hypotheses on the strengthening system, such as perfect adhesion between wall and reinforcement and also between matrix and fibres of the strengthening system are adopted. Such hypotheses allow to improve the existing discrete model without increasing the overall number of degrees of freedom involved in the numerical tests but allowing to add further stiffness and strength parameters accounting to NFRCM mechanical properties. The proposed model turns out to simulate cracking both on masonry and on the external reinforcing layers. Then, it is compared and calibrated with respect to a second numerical model, namely a FEM based on smeared crack theory, which considers a whole homogenization for masonry [7] and NFRCM material [4] as a simplified modelling alternative. The numerical approaches are compared and calibrated by

reproducing several shear tests on NFRCM strengthened masonry panels. The differences and similarities of input parameters and results given by both numerical models are analysed and critically compared, aiming to evaluate the applicability and reliability of the updated discrete model by reference to the homogeneous one.

Case Study Typology

Reinforced masonry panel. This contribution considers one leaf masonry wall characterized by a regular texture of standard blocks (Fig. 1a) reinforced on both sides by NFRCM layers having the same thickness t (Fig. 1b). Reinforcement layers are considered on both sides of the original masonry panel in order to have a symmetric model along its thickness, in this case in plane and out of plane effects are uncoupled. Reinforcement layers are made of natural fibers embedded in a mortar layer. In particular, this work considers the NFRCM system already proposed in [4], constituted by a 10 mm thick mortar matrix and a Sisal plain-woven textile reinforcement (mesh 10 mm x 10mm) placed in the middle of the whole thickness, embedded in the mortar layer. It is worth noting that the plain-woven textile reinforcement is aligned with vertical and horizontal main directions of the panel.

Fig. 1 – (a) Unreinforced masonry panel (URM), (b) Reinforced masonry panel (RM)

Numerical Models

Updated discrete element model. The discrete element model here proposed is based on an existing discrete element or rigid block model, recently refined by authors by accounting for potential cracking of both mortar joints and blocks [5]. This model is further upgraded at this stage by considering the effect of external reinforcement layers, placed on both sides of the original masonry panel and over the entire panel surface. Perfect adhesion between reinforcement layers and masonry wall is assumed as a further hypothesis of the model.

Masonry panel. A one-leaf masonry panel with regular texture is considered (Fig 1a). Block dimensions are width b , height a , and thickness s ; mortar joint thickness is e , assumed to be equal for both head (vertical) and bed (horizontal) joints. The refined rigid block model is characterized by subdividing each block in two half-blocks (Fig. 2a). The resulting discretization is characterized by elements aligned both horizontally and vertically and in contact with four neighboring half-blocks by means of four interfaces coincident with the four half-block edges. Horizontal interfaces are always represented by mortar interfaces, whereas vertical interfaces can be, alternatively, mortar interfaces or inner block interfaces; the latter interface case may represent a potential vertical crack in the block. A two-dimensional coordinate system Oy_1y_2 is assumed, the in-plane displacement of each half block

$B_{i,j}$ is a rigid body motion defined by half block center in-plane translations and half block in-plane rotation $\mathbf{q}_{ij} = \{u_1 \ u_2 \ \omega_3\}^T_{ij}$. The interactions between the half blocks, given by the resultants of the corresponding interface contact stresses, are normal force, shear force and bending moment $\mathbf{f}_m = \{F_n \ F_s \ M\}^T_m$, which depend on half-block relative displacements $\mathbf{d} = \{d_n \ d_s \ \delta\}^T$ by means of elastic-plastic constitutive laws accounting for joint stiffness ($\mathbf{f}_m = \mathbf{K}_m \mathbf{d}$, with $\mathbf{K}_m = \text{diag}\{k_n \ k_s \ k_\delta\}_m$) and strength ($\mathbf{f}_m \leq \mathbf{f}_{m,\text{lim}}$) depending on mortar and brick mechanical characteristics. Softening behaviour is assumed for tensile and shear cracking as proposed with the refined model [5]. Joint relative displacements depend on half-block degrees of freedom by means of a compatibility matrix \mathbf{H} that collects the relative distances between half-block and joint centres [5].

Fig. 2 – (a) refined discrete model for a representative elementary volume of masonry, (b) corresponding discretization for the reinforcement layers

Reinforcement layers. As previously stated, two equal reinforcement layers are placed on both sides of the masonry panel (Fig. 1b) and the same behaviour in terms of displacements and internal actions is assumed for them. In this way, the resultant of the actions transmitted by the reinforcements to the masonry panel acts along panel middle-plane, allowing to perform in-plane analyses without considering out-of-plane effects. Furthermore, full adhesion between masonry wall and reinforcement layers is assumed at this stage of the research, in order avoid the definition of further displacement fields for describing the behaviour of the external layers. Due to this hypothesis, each reinforcement layer is subdivided into quadrilateral portions having the same size of the half-blocks of the masonry panel (Fig 2b), then the rigid body displacements \mathbf{q}_{ij} introduced for the half-blocks are also adopted for describing the displacements of external layer portions. The actions transmitted by the reinforcement to the blocks are considered in the same manner of the masonry panel $\mathbf{f}_r = \{F_n \ F_s \ M\}^T_r$, depending on the relative displacements between reinforcement portions ($\mathbf{f}_r = \mathbf{K}_r \mathbf{d}$, with $\mathbf{K}_r = \text{diag}\{k_n \ k_s \ k_\delta\}_r$), which are coincident with half-block relative displacements thanks to the no-slip hypothesis. In this case, the deformability of the reinforcement layers is modelled by means of one-dimensional springs connecting portion centres. Stiffness \mathbf{K}_r and strength $\mathbf{f}_{r,\text{lim}}$ parameters for the springs are deduced from the homogenization procedure already done in [4] for defining the multi-layer FE model, accounting for stiffness and strength of mortar matrix and embedded textile. Thanks to the regular subdivision of the panel, horizontal and vertical springs have the same mechanical characteristics per unit area.

Furthermore, the forces transmitted by reinforcement layers to portion centres are added to the forces transmitted between the half-blocks, $\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}_m + \mathbf{f}_r$, allowing to perform numerical analyses by setting the equilibrium between external dead and live nodal loads and internal actions.

Homogenized FE model. The FE model for representing the reinforced masonry panel was already introduced in [4]. The homogenization of reinforced masonry is obtained by integrating the constitutive functions of masonry and NFRCM along the thickness of the wall [7], hence by determining the weighted average of masonry and NFRCM homogenized moduli along wall thickness.

Then, the model considers a unique homogenized material and adopts quadrilateral 8-noded elements in plane stress state [8]. The element thickness is equal to the whole thickness of URM and RM panels. Material elastic parameters are assigned in agreement with a homogenization procedure, and a total strain rotating crack model (TRSCM) is used for representing the nonlinear behavior, which is characterized by a parabolic response in compression and an exponential response in tension. The inelastic parameters – tensile and compressive strength, fracture energy in compression and tension – are assumed in the following numerical tests accordingly to the existing literature [9].

Numerical Tests

Pushover tests. Numerical pushover analyses of a reinforced masonry (RM) panel are performed by adopting the updated discrete model and the homogenized FE model. The unreinforced cases (URM) are also considered by adopting the original refined discrete model and a homogenized FEM. Unreinforced and reinforced masonry panels are subjected to an increasing horizontal displacement applied along the upper edge and the boundary conditions are assumed fixed at the bottom and sliding at the top. A rigid beam is placed on the top of the panel to distribute uniformly the horizontal displacement and avoid vertical relative displacements (Fig. 3).

Block dimensions are width $b = 120$ mm, height $a = 55$ mm, thickness $s = 250$ mm, mortar joint thickness is $e = 10$ mm. Panel overall dimensions are width $B = 1160$ mm, height $H = 1160$ mm, given by 9 blocks along panel length and 18 courses of blocks along panel height. Each reinforcement layer is characterized by thickness $t = 10$ mm.

Elastic and inelastic parameters of URM and RM panels, adopted for the numerical models, are collected in Table 1. Further details can be found in [4,10].

Table 1 – Mechanical properties of URM and RM material components

Mechanical parameters		Blocks	DEM			FEM
			Mortar	NFRCM	RM	(homogeneous)
Elastic modulus	E [MPa]	-	500	2000	4384	
Poisson's ratio	ν	-	0.2	0.2	0.18	
Tensile strength	f_t [MPa]	1.0	0.5	2.5	0.02	
Fracture energy - tension	G_I [N/mm]	0.1	0.04	0.04	0.025	
Compressive strength	f_c [MPa]	14.0	4.0	13.0	5.16	
Fracture energy - compression	G_c [N/mm]	-	-	-	8.17	
Friction ratio	μ	1	0.7	0.7	-	
Cohesion	c [MPa]	1.4	0.7	3.5	-	
Fracture energy - shear	G_{II} [N/mm]	-	0.2	0.8	-	

Results discussion. Fig. 4 collects the load-displacement curves obtained with the discrete model (dashed lines) and with the homogeneous FEM (continuous lines). Discrete and homogeneous models turn out to be in excellent agreement during the initial elastic phase of the test, whereas after the first level of damage, the original and updated discrete models turn out to be stiffer than the homogeneous FE models.

Fig. 3 – Case study: applied displacement and boundary conditions considered on masonry panel (URM case)

It should be noted that homogeneous FE models are characterized by a significant ductile behaviour after reaching the maximum shear load. This difference is justified by the rigid block hypothesis adopted by the discrete model, which can be overcome by reducing the stiffness of the interfaces of the masonry panel accounting for block elastic modulus [11]. Furthermore, the discrete model is still not able to correctly represent the softening behaviour of masonry in compression, hence numerical tests are stopped before observing compressive failure of mortar interfaces and reinforcement springs. However, the maximum shear strength attained both by URM and RM panels modelled by the discrete model is in good agreement with the strength obtained with the homogeneous FEM. In particular, both numerical models show a similar shear strength increment given by the NFRCM (from 129 kN to 184 kN with the discrete model, from 142 kN to 187 kN with the homogeneous FEM).

Fig. 4 – Load-displacement curves for URM and RM cases obtained with the proposed numerical models

Fig. 5a shows the deformed configuration of the URM panel close to the end of the pushover test, whereas Fig. 5b highlights the corresponding damage given by a diagonal crack involving mortar joints and some inner-block interfaces.

Fig. 6a shows the deformed configuration of the RM panel close to the end of the pushover test, which is quite similar to that obtained with the URM case, but it is characterized by a larger shear strength. The diagonal crack involving mortar and inner block joints in Fig. 6b is defined by a slightly small number of damaged interfaces with respect to the URM case, thanks to the reinforcement layers. These layers allow to increase the overall strength of the panel and are characterized by a less evident diagonal crack, showed in Fig. 6c, with respect to the masonry panel. Then, the overall number of damaged interfaces of the RM case is larger than that of URM; furthermore, damaged interfaces are located close to the diagonal direction of the square panel and turn out to be in good agreement with the damage pattern obtained with the homogeneous FEM [4].

Fig. 5 – URM panel: deformed configuration (a) and interface damage (b) close to the end of the numerical test

Fig. 6 – RM panel: deformed configuration (a), masonry interface damage (b), reinforcement damage (c) close to the end of the numerical test

Final Considerations

The preliminary test performed in this research showed the effectiveness of the proposed updated discrete model in representing the behaviour of in-plane loaded NFRCM reinforced masonry panels. The representation of reinforcement layers by means of one-dimensional springs, even if simplified, allowed the discrete element model to successfully account for the strength increment, however it is not able to correctly reproduce the ductility increment given by the reinforcement.

Further developments of the discrete model will focus on a better representation of the compressive nonlinear behaviour of mortar joints, inner block joints and also reinforcement layers, in order to better reproduce the softening behaviour of both URM and RM after reaching the maximum shear strength. Numerical tests, performed both with discrete element and homogeneous FE models, will be also compared with existing laboratory tests of masonry panels reinforced with NFRCM [12]. Particular attention will be given to the calibration of model parameters starting from those of constituent materials, in order to both reproduce load-displacement results and actual damage patterns.

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